

Perception and Acceptability Towards Administration of Anthelmintic Drugs to School Pupils Among Traders in Olomi Market, Ibadan

AUTHOR(S): KADRI, Adenike Koseganlola Risikat (RN, PhD), NGADI Yvette-Ella Adanna (RN, BNSc), OLALEYE, Christiana Oluwatoyi (RN, MSc), AYANLEKE, Ismail Adebare (RN, MSc), JIMOH, Esther Ozichu (RN, MSc), BELLO, Salihu Sule (RN, BNSc),

Abstract:

Helminthiasis being a global health burden and is attributed as one of the Neglected Tropical Diseases (NTDs) by medical and international community results to ill-health. The study assessed the perception and acceptability towards administration of anthelmintic drugs to school pupils among traders in Olomi market, Ibadan. Health Belief Model was used for this study and relevant literatures were reviewed. The theory that was adopted for the study was Health belief Model. This study adopted cross-sectional research design, One hundred (100) traders in Olomi market were selected from the total population of traders in the market. Purposive sampling technique was used to select respondents for this study. Three research questions were answered and one hypothesis was tested. A self-developed and validated questionnaire with reliability coefficient of 0.78 was used to collect data for the study. Data generated was analysed using descriptive statistics of frequency counts and percentages, interpreted into charts and tables as well as inferential statistics of chi-square. Ethical consideration was ensured and ethical approval was sought. Majority 35(35%) respondents were between 30 years and 39 years, 72 were Christians, 70 were Yorubas, 25 had post secondary education, 49 respondents were married, 30(30%) of the respondents said they strongly agreed this implies that majority of the respondents are in support of deworming children. 71 have heard helminthic drugs, 63 of the total respondents have received health education or sensitization on anthelmintic drugs, 63(63%) of

CJARAccepted 5 January 2025
Published 10 January 2025
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14641633

the respondents agreed that the programme is acceptable to them and positive perception about helminthic drugs. In conclusion, the respondents accepted the use of helminthic drugs but negative perception towards helminthic drugs. For there is no parental concept. Based on findings of the study, it is recommended that parents and caregivers should be informed through any means to receive their blessings to collect the drugs for their children in order to prevent health problems as a result of helminthiasis.

Keywords: Perception, Acceptability, Anthelmintic Drugs, School Pupils, Traders,

About Author

Author(s): KADRI, Adenike Koseganlola Risikat (RN, PhD)

Kadri.adenike@lcu.edu.ng

Lead City University, Ibadan

NGADI Yvette-Ella Adanna (RN, BNSc)

Lead City University, Ibadan

OLALEYE, Christiana Oluwatoyi (RN, MSc)

Lead City University, Ibadan

AYANLEKE, Ismail Adebare (RN, MSc)

lekefortune@gmail.com

Nursing and Midwifery Council of Nigeria, Abuja

JIMOH, Esther Ozichu (RN, MSc)

University College Hospital, Ibadan

BELLO, Salihu Sule (RN, BNSc)

Kogi State College of Nursing and Midwifery Obangede

Introduction

Helminthiasis being a global health burden and is attributed as one of the Neglected Tropical Diseases (NTDs) by medical and international community results to ill-health (WHO, 2020). They are the major health problems in the tropical and subtropical parts of the world where temperature, humidity, lack of hygiene, poverty, socio-cultural habits and demographic factors favour their development (Payne, Lontuo, Ngangnang, Megwi and Mbong, 2019). They are responsible for considerable morbidity and in severe cases, cause mortality (Kongs, Marks, Verle and Van Der Stuyft, 2021). Previous studies indicate that the Neglected Tropical Diseases (NTDs) are widespread among the poor in the Sub Saharan Africa (SSA) (Molyneux, Hotez and Fenwick, 2019). These parasites dwell in the gastrointestinal tract in humans and other animals. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that over 2 billion individuals suffer from parasitic infections worldwide, resulting to more than 155,000 thousand deaths per year with 97% of these deaths occurring in the developed parts of the world (Onwuliri, Anosike, Nkem and Payne, 2019).

These infections are higher in Children and the elderly than in middle-aged individuals and between immigrants and refugees (Bethony, Brooker, Albonico, Geiger and Loukas, 2018). *Ascaris lumbricoides* a cosmopolitan nematode affects over 1.5 billion people, followed by *Ankylostoma* 1 billion and *T. trichiura* 800 million people throughout the world (Benedict, 2020). These intestinal infections caused severe intestinal disorder such as dysentery; diarrhoea, mild abdominal pain, vomiting, and lack of appetite and in some cases lead to mental retardation in children and even affect physical growth and development Diakite (2018). In Cameroon, a report from the Cameroonian Public Health Secretary of State revealed that 16.1 million inhabitants with more than 10 million suffer from helminthiasis. The prevalence and intensity of these infections fluctuates from one region to the other MINSANTE (2019). Since 2001, STHs endemic countries have been urged during the 54th World Health Organization (WHO, 2021) assembly to implement periodic and regular deworming of at least once or twice every year among school-aged children and other groups at risk of morbidity in order to eliminate morbidity of STHs in children by 2020 through school-based deworming.

The Benzimidazole group usually a single oral dose of Albendazole (400 mg) or Mebendazole (500 mg) is the most widely distributed among the population. Cameroon adopted the strategic plan for the control of schistosomiasis and STHs in 2004, however the nationwide school-based deworming is still in progress (Tchuem, Dongmo, Ngassam, Kenfack, Feussom (2019). From this report, the prevalence and intensity of gastrointestinal parasites in Cameroon is high and the control programs against these infections among school-aged children is effective in some regions than others, while in other regions, divisions and sub-divisions, prevalence, intensity and the efficacy of anthelmintic drugs against these infections are not really known. Soil-transmitted helminth infections are usually asymptomatic and the manifestations of these infections are not fatal, contrary to the protozoan's infections which is symptomatic and fatal.

This might be the reason why STHs has not received proper attention in research findings and public recognition. Some related effects of STHs is that; they reduced the functioning system of the body, physical performance is reduced and poor cognitivity in children resulting to a decrease in human financial capital among adults of the infected population

(Payne, Lontuo, Ngangnang, Megwi and Mbong, 2019). Given the huge impact of these diseases and the alarming number of people affected by them all over the world, this thesis focuses on the perception. And acceptability towards administration of anthelmintics to school pupils among traders in Olomi market, Ibadan.

Statement of the Problem

Drug revolving scheme, is a mean of providing comprehensive health care services and with the growing belief that people ought to receive medical care for humanitarian reasons, regardless of their ability to pay. Medical care services for humanitarian is well known to number of people, published in the electronic and print media, through conferences, seminars, workshops, stage and storytelling both traditionally and orthodox ways of instructions, but unfortunately this has not been well understood, and the attitude towards the effectiveness of drug appears the same because of the primitive perception of the people. Therefore, there is need to find out the perception and acceptability towards administration of anti-helminthic drugs to school pupils among traders in Olomi market, Ibadan

Research Questions

1. What is the perception towards administration of anthelmintic drugs to school students among traders in Olomi market, Ibadan?
2. What is the acceptability towards administration of anthelmintic drugs to school students among traders in Olomi market, Ibadan?
3. What are the factors influencing factors influencing the respondents' acceptability of anthelmintic drugs administration of anthelmintic drugs to school students among traders in Olomi market, Ibadan?

Hypothesis: There is no significant correlation between perception and acceptability of anthelmintic drugs and respondents.

Materials and Methods

This study adopted descriptive cross-sectional research design, One hundred (100) traders in Olomi market were selected from the total population of traders in the market. Purposive sampling technique was used to select respondents for this study. Three research questions were answered and one hypothesis was tested. A self-developed and validated questionnaire with reliability coefficient of 7.8 was used to collect data for the study. Data generated was analysed using descriptive statistics of frequency counts and percentages, interpreted into charts and tables as well as inferential statistics of chi-square. Ethical consideration was ensured and ethical approval was sought. The research instrument used was questionnaire.

A structured, pretested self-developed questionnaire was used to gather information about acceptability and perception on administration of anthelmintic drugs to school pupils among traders in Olomi market, Ibadan. The questionnaires was divided into five sections "A, B, C, D"

Section A: on i socio-demographic data of the respondents, **section B:** about anthelmintic drugs, **section D:** acceptability of administration of anthelmintic drugs. **Section E:** factors influencing the respondents' acceptability of anthelmintic drugs.

The instrument was given to my project supervisor, other lecturers in and out of my department for vetting after which the instrument was collected back and corrections and proper check up were effected before the final copies were produced. The reliability of the instrument was done through test – retest method. The questionnaire was administered twice on twenty (20) respondents drawn from the market, which were not part of the target

population but possess the same characteristics with the target population and it yielded the same results which shows that the instrument is reliable. The instrument was shared among the respondents personally by the researcher and research assistants and collected back immediately. Data collation was done after the collection of the completed questionnaire. The variables were sorted out and arranged according to the aims of the study. The data was presented in frequency distribution tables and cross-tabulation.

Ethical consideration: Ethical approval was sought from institution ethical board and ethical principles were ensured and applied to collect data for the study.

Results

Table 1: Socio-demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Demographic Characteristics	Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age	20 - 29years	23	23
	30 - 39years	35	35
	40 - 49years	32	32
	50years and above	10	10
Religion	Christian	72	72
	Muslim	28	28
	Traditional	9	9
	Others	0	0
Ethnicity	Hausa	9	9
	Yoruba	70	70
	Igbo	8	8
	Others	13	13
Educational Qualification	Primary	23	23
	Secondary	20	20
	College of education	25	25
	Polytechnic	14	14
	University	18	18
Marital Status	Single	27	27
	Married	49	49
	Separated	2	2
	Divorced	22	22
Do you have children?	Yes	83	83
	No	17	17
If yes, how many?	1	15	15
	2	26	26
	3	49	49
	4	5	5
Have you receive health education or sensitization on anthelmintic drugs?	Yes	63	63
	No	37	37

Table 1 above show that 23 (23%) out of the total respondents were between 20 years and 29 years of age, 35(35%) respondents were between 30 years and 39 years, 32(32%) respondents were between 40 years and 49 years, while the remaining 10 (10%) respondents were between 50years and above. This implies that majority of the respondents are in their active years. The table also shows that 72(72%) of the respondents were Christians, 28(28%) respondents were Muslims, while the remaining 9(9%) of the respondents were traditional worshipers. The table further shows that 9(9%) of the total respondents were Hausa, 70(70%) respondents were Yoruba, 8 (8%) respondents were Igbo while the remaining 13 (13%) respondents were from other tribe. This implies that majority of the respondents were Yoruba. The table also reveal that 23(23%) out of the total respondents had primary education, 20(20%) had first secondary certificate, 25(25%) had college of education, 14(14%) of the respondents had were polytechnic graduate while 18(18%) had universities certificates.

The table also revealed that 27(27%) of the total respondents were single, 49(4%) of the respondents were married, 2(2%) of the respondents were separated while 22(22%) of the respondents were divorced. This implies that majority of the respondents were married. The table also reveal that 83(83%) of the respondents are mothers while the remaining 17(17%) were still women without babies. Furthermore, the table describes the respondents according to the number of child given birth to, 15(15%) of the respondents had a child, 26(2%) of the respondents had 2 children, 49 (49%) of the respondents had 3 children, 5(5%) of the respondents had 4 children, 2(2%) of the respondents had 5children while the remaining 3(3%) of the respondents had six children.

The table also reveal that 63(6%) of the total respondents have receive health education or sensitization on anthelmintic drugs while 37(37%) of the respondents have nit receive any health education or sensitization. This implies that majority of the respondents have received health education or sensitization on anthelmintic drugs.

Research Question One: What are the respondents sources of information on Anthelmintic drugs?

Table 2: Sources of Information about Anthelmintic Drugs

Items	Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Have you heard of anthelmintic drugs?	Yes	71	71
	No	29	29
	Don't know	0	0
What is your main source of information on Anthelmintic drugs?	Clinic/Hospital servant	17	17
	Radio	10	10
	Television	4	4
	Market	25	25
	Group Discussion	9	9
	Friend	6	6
When did you hear about it?	Less than a month	0	0
	1-6 month	7	7
	7-12 months	10	10
	13-16 months	24	24

	17-24 months	13	13
	above 2 years	17	17
Is the program acceptable to you?	Yes	43	43
	No	28	28

The Table 2 above shows that 71 (71%) respondents have heard of heard of anthelmintic drugs while 29(29%) of the respondents said they haven't heard of anthelmintic drugs. This implies that majority of the respondents have the full knowledge of anthelmintic drugs. The table further reveals the source of information on anthelmintic drugs, 17(17%) of the total respondents said from clinic/hospital servant, 10(10%) of the respondents said through radio, 4(4%) of the respondents said through television, 25(2%) of the respondents said in the market place, 9(9%) of the respondents said through group discussion while the remaining 6(6%) of the respondents said through friends. This implies that majority of the respondents got the information in the market place. The table also reveals that none of the respondents heard about anthelmintic drugs within a month to the time of this research, 7(7%) of the respondents said between 1-6 months, 10(10%) of the respondents said between 7-12 months, 24(24%) of the respondents said between 13-16months, 13(13%) of the respondents said between 17-24months while the remaining 17(17%) of the respondents said above two years. Finally, 43(43%) of the respondents agreed that the program is acceptable to them while the remaining 28(28%) of the respondents disagreed with it.

Research Question Two: What are the respondents perception on the administration of anthelmintic drugs to school pupils?

Table 3: Perception of the Administration of Anthelmintic Drugs

Variables	Agree (%)	Strongly Agree (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly Disagree (%)
Do you believe in deworming your child/children?	27 (27%)	30 (30%)	20 (20%)	23 (23%)
Do you believe that deworming a child can improve their growth?	23 (23%)	29 (29%)	27 (27%)	21 (21%)
Does your perception of Anthelmintic drugs change upon usage?	33 (33%)	19 (19%)	21 (21%)	27 (27%)
Does your perception of Anthelmintic drugs change upon usage?	33 (33%)	19 (19%)	21 (21%)	27 (27%)
Do you agree that it is proper for the government to allow distribution of Anthelmintic drugs?	30 (30%)	37 (37%)	19 (19%)	14 (14%)
Do you agree that health workers should distribute the Anthelmintic drugs?	14 (14%)	57 (57%)	13 (13%)	16 (16%)

The table represented above shows that 27(27%) of the respondents believed in deworming child/children, 30(30%) of the respondents said they strongly agreed with it, 20(20%) of the respondents said they disagreed while the remaining 23(23%) of the respondents strongly

disagreed with it. This implies that majority of the respondents are in support of deworming child/children. The table further shows that 23(23%) of the respondents believed that deworming a child can improve their growth, 29(29%) of the respondents said they strongly agreed with it, 27(27%) of the respondents said they disagreed while the remaining 21(21%) of the respondents strongly disagreed with it. This implies that majority of the respondents are in support that deworming child/children can improve their growth.

The table also reveals that 33(33%) of the respondents agreed that their perception of anthelmintic drugs change upon usage, 19(19%) of the respondents strongly agreed to the change, 21(21%) of the respondents disagreed while the remaining 27(27%) of the respondents strongly disagreed. From the table, 30(30%) of the respondents agreed that it is proper for the government to allow distribution of Anthelmintic drugs, 37(37%) of the respondents also strongly agreed with it, 19(19%) disagreed that it is proper for the government to allow distribution of Anthelmintic drugs said they disagreed that it is proper for the government to allow distribution of Anthelmintic drugs while the remaining 14(14%) of the respondents said they strongly disagreed. Finally, on the table, 14(14%) of the respondents agreed that health workers should distribute the anthelmintic drugs, 57(57%) of the respondents are on the same opinion as they strongly agreed with it, 13(13%) of the respondents disagreed with the opinion as also 16(16%) of the remaining respondents strongly disagreed to the above point.

Research Question Three: What are the respondents acceptability of the administration of anthelmintic drugs?

Table 4: Acceptability of Administration of Anthelmintic Drugs

Variables	Agree (%)	Strongly Agree (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly Disagree (%)
Do you advise that Anthelmintic should be prescribed when needed?	24 (24%)	35 (35%)	28 (28%)	13 (13%)
Do you advise that Anthelmintic should be prescribed when needed?	24 (24%)	35 (35%)	28 (28%)	13 (13%)
Do you think the drugs was effective to the purpose it was taken?	22 (22%)	32 (32%)	27 (27%)	19 (19%)
Do you consider the use of Anthelmintic Drugs in Children?	21 (21%)	37 (37%)	24 (24%)	18 (18%)
Do you consider the use of Anthelmintic drugs to be allergic to you?	14 (14%)	35 (35%)	26 (26%)	25 (25%)

The table represented above shows that 24(24%) of the respondents agreed that Anthelmintic should be prescribed when needed, 35(35%) of the respondents said they strongly agreed with it, 28(28%) of the respondents said they disagreed that Anthelmintic should be prescribed when needed while the remaining 13(13%) of the respondents strongly disagreed with it. This implies that majority of the respondents are in support that Anthelmintic should be prescribed when needed. The table further shows that 22(22%) of the respondents agreed that the drugs was effective to the purpose it was taken, 32(32%) of the respondents also said that they strongly agreed with it, 27(27%) of the respondents said they

disagreed while the remaining 19(19%) of the respondents strongly disagreed with it. This implies that majority of the respondents are in support that the drugs was effective. The table also reveals that 21(21%) of the respondents agreed that their children should use anthelmintic drugs, 37(37%) of the respondents strongly agreed to the usage, 24(24%) of the respondents disagreed with the while the remaining 18(18%) of the respondents strongly disagreed. From the same table, 14(14%) of the respondents agreed that the use of anthelmintic drugs is allergic to them, 35(35%) strongly agreed with the opinion, 26(26%) disagreed that anthelmintic drugs is allergic to them while the remaining 25(25%) of the respondents said they strongly disagreed.

Research Question Four: What are the factors influencing the respondents acceptability of the anthelmintic drugs?

Table 5: Factors Influencing Acceptability of the Administration of Anthelmintic Drugs

Variables	Agree (%)	Strongly Agree (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly Disagree (%)
Do you believe that price, religious beliefs and otherwise can influence your perception on Anthelmintic drugs?	15 (15%)	48 (48%)	23 (23%)	14 (14%)
Does family practice on drug usage influence your decision on the use of Anthelmintic drugs?	33 (33%)	15 (15%)	27 (27%)	25 (25%)
Does availability on the drugs influence your usage of Anthelmintic drugs?	27 (27%)	17 (17%)	25 (25%)	31 (31%)
In the case of any epidemic do you agree that the usage of Anthelmintic drugs would've prevented it?	20 (20%)	28 (28%)	22 (22%)	30 (30%)

The table represented above shows that 15(15%) of the respondents believed that price, religious beliefs and otherwise can influence your perception on Anthelmintic drugs, 48(48%) of the respondents said they also strongly agreed with it, 23(23%) of the respondents said they disagreed to the believed that price, religious beliefs and otherwise can influence your perception on Anthelmintic drugs while the remaining 14(14%) of the respondents strongly disagreed with it. The table further shows that 33(33%) of the respondents believed that their family practice on drug usage influence their decision on the use of Anthelmintic drugs, 15(15%) of the respondents said they also strongly agreed with it, 27(27%) of the respondents said they disagreed that their family practice on drug usage influence their decision on the use of Anthelmintic drugs while the remaining 25(25%) of the respondents strongly disagreed with it. This implies that majority of the respondents are not in support that their family practice on drug usage influence their decision on the use of Anthelmintic drugs.

The table also reveals that 27(27%) of the respondents agreed that the availability on the drugs influence their usage of Anthelmintic drugs, 17 (17%) of the respondents strongly agreed to the same view, 25(25%) of the respondents disagreed that the availability on the drugs influence your usage of Anthelmintic drugs while the remaining 31(31%) of the

respondents also strongly disagreed. Finally, on the item of in the case of any epidemic do you agree that the usage of Anthelmintic drugs would've prevented it, 20(20%) of the respondents agreed to it, 28(28%) of the respondents are on the same opinion as they strongly agreed with it, 22(22%) of the respondents disagreed with the opinion as also 30(30%) of the remaining respondents strongly disagreed to the above point.

Discussion of Findings

The total number of one hundred mothers with their infants was studied. The socio-demographic characteristics of the mothers represented in Table 4.1 showed that majority of the mothers (35%) were within the age range of 30-39years. This is in line with the studies of Filippo (2018) and Akorede & Abiola (2017) who said that mothers within the age of 30 to 39 years were in the best positioned to adequately cater for the wellbeing of their children. This is as a result that they are full of strength and agile in carrying out their duties as expected. Also, the major ethnic group studied in this work is the Yoruba; this might be due to the fact that the study was carried out within the Yoruba metropolis. From this study, it can also be deduced that most of the respondents have knowledge of the formal education and this aid their understanding about anthelmintic drugs. The table also showed that majority of the respondents was married.

From this study, it was revealed that the majority of the respondents have received health education or sensitization on anthelmintic drugs. This is also in line with the study of with WHO (2019) second edition on helminth control in school-based children. According to them, the advertisement and seminars given to mothers is enough for them to have the full knowledge of anthelmintic drugs. Furthermore, it was also discovered that health workers are up and doing in the spreading of the information relating to health issues which anthelmintic drugs usage is not exceptional. The study also shows that majority of the respondents (71%) have adequate knowledge of anthelmintic drugs. This is in accordance with the study carried out by Khan (2020), it was discovered that in urban area, majority of the communities have adequate knowledge of anthelmintic drugs. This also corroborate with the WHO (2020) edition on anthelmintic drugs. From the study, it was revealed that the major source of information about anthelmintic drugs is within the market women in the market place.

This relate with the study carried by Alfredo (2021) on the treatment of helminth infections. According to the study, the women in the public place often shared information within themselves especially issues relating to the wards. This is in line with the findings of this study as it was revealed that the market women got the information about anthelmintic drugs. This can be to the factor that market women spend more time together than they relate with other people in their houses. Just as the researcher got to know that most women stay in the market from morning till night. They only go to their various houses to sleep and report to the market the following day. So, it is not surprising that they got the information within themselves.

From the information gathered in this study, it was discovered that majority of the mothers (24%) had the information about anthelmintic drugs for over a year. This might be due to the time of duration spent in the market as that is their daily working place. This could also be because the market is always full of different information on a daily basis. The information from the questionnaires and the focus group discussions gives an indication that the mothers

receive good education about anthelmintic drugs. The high number of women (72%) accepting anthelmintic drugs may probably be linked to the fact that the majority had a strong believe in whatever information the receive in the market place. It has been shown that women tend to be more believe in themselves than they do with others (Gbolahan, 2019).

Furthermore, this study confirmed that majority of the women (57%) believed in deworming children and that it also deworming children improve their growth. This signified that majority of the women had the understanding of the importance of anthelmintic drugs. This study is also in line with the study of Alfredo (2021) who agreed that women who cares much for their children do have more understanding about health related issues and therefore, acceptance is not a difficult thing for them. As earlier said based on findings of this study, most of the studied mothers accept the usage of anthelmintic drugs. This is in line with 68.3% in Ile-ife, Southwestern, Nigeria (Adejuyigbe, Orji, Onayade, Makinde and Anyabolu, 2018) and this may be because the studies were from the same region of the country.

The proportion of mothers who have a changed practice of perception of anthelmintic drugs after usage (13.0%) gave an instinct that the practice is guaranteed just as in Oladokun, Brown, and Osinusi, (2015) who said women do put into practice what they tend to believe not what they are told. This may be due to the setting where Oladokun, Brown and Osinusi carried out their study. The study also discovered that majority of the women are in support of the distribution of anthelmintic drugs. This might be to the fact that women often have interest of free things rather than spending their money in buying them.

The result of this study on the acceptability of administration of anthelmintic drugs was on the high side. As majority of the women (59%) advised that anthelmintic drugs should be prescribed when needed, this is in support of the study of Adeyinka (2019) on the acceptability of helminth drugs. His study revealed that most women have the knowledge of anthelmintic drugs often accept it than the numbers of them that reject it. The findings of this study further showed that the factors influencing the acceptability of the administration of anthelmintic drugs are family practice with 52% and availability of the drugs (66%). This is in support of the study of Saliu (2020) who said the availability of anthelmintic drugs is a major factor that influence it usage.

Conclusion

There is need for health workers to be knowledgeable about the need for Anthelmintic Drug and to spread the information. There is need for the health workers to attend to the patients politely. There is need for the patients to feed the health workers back about the drugs given or prescribed to them after used.

Recommendations

It is recommended that each child be given a food (e.g. a slice of bread or a biscuit) before the drug under investigation is administered. It is essential that the drugs administered are within the expiry date and properly stored. WHO can provide limited quantities of drugs for evaluations of efficacy. The tablet should be ingested under direct observation by the distributor, and the child should be maintained under observation for approximately 4 hours. The children can remain at school and continue their usual activities, but they should rapidly report any side-effect to a member of the investigation team. A child who vomits after drug

administration should be excluded from the analysis because the precise amount of anthelmintic drug he or she consumed will be unknown.

References

- Benedict, M. (2020). The influence of intestinal parasites on academic performance among primary school children in Nairobi province, Kenya. [Master's thesis, Kenyatta University].
- Bethony, J., Brooker, S., Albonico, M., Geiger, S. M., Loukas, A., et al. (2021). Soil-transmitted helminth infections: Ascariasis, trichuriasis, and hookworm. *Lancet*, *367*, 1521–1532.
- Bethony, J., Brooker, S., Albonico, M., et al. (2022). Soil-transmitted helminth infections: Ascariasis, trichuriasis, and hookworm. *Lancet*, *367*(9521), 1521–1532.
- Diakite, A. (2021). Les parasitoses digestives chez les patients hospitalisés dans services de médecine de l'Hôpital Nationale du Point G. [Doctoral thesis, Faculté de Médecine, de Pharmacie et d'Odontostomatologie, Bamako-Mali].
- Kongs, A., Marks, G., Verle, P., & Van Der Stuyft, P. (2021). The unreliability of the Kato-Katz technique limits its usefulness for evaluating *S. mansoni* infections. *Tropical Medicine and International Health*, *6*, 163–169.
- MINSANTE. (2022). Programme Nationale de lutte contre Schistosomiase et les helminth intestinale: Plan stratégique 2020-2022. Ministre de la Santé Publique Cameroun.
- Molyneux, D. H., Hotez, P. J., & Fenwick, A. (2022). "Rapid-impact interventions": How a policy of integrated control for Africa's neglected tropical diseases could benefit the poor. *PLoS Medicine*, *2*, e336.
- National Drug Policy for Nigeria Ministry of Health. (2022). Drug information and promotion (p. 24).
- Onwuliri, C. O., Anosike, J. C., Nkem, C. N., & Payne, V. K. (2022). The ecology of animal parasitic nematodes in endemic areas of Jos, Nigeria. *Applied Parasitology*, *34*, 131–137.
- Payne, K., Lontuo, F., Ngangngang, G., Megwi, L., Mbong, E., et al. (2022). Prevalence and intensity of infection of gastrointestinal parasites in Babadjou, West Region of Cameroon. *International Journal of Clinical and Experimental Medical Sciences*, *3*, 14–22.
- Tchuem, A., Dongmo, N., Ngassam, P., Kenfack, C., Feussom, G., et al. (2022). Mapping of schistosomiasis and soil-transmitted helminthiasis in the regions of Littoral, North-West, South, and South-West Cameroon and recommendations for treatment. *BMC Infectious Diseases*, *13*, 602.
- World Health Organization. (2020). *Eliminating soil-transmitted helminthiasis as a public health problem in children: Progress report 2020–2022*.
- World Health Organization. (2021). *Coordinated use of anthelmintic drugs in control interventions: A manual for health professionals and programme managers* (D. Engels, Ed.). Geneva.
- World Health Organization. (2021). *Female genital schistosomiasis: A pocket atlas for clinical health-care professionals*. Geneva.
- World Health Organization. (2021). *Prevention and control of schistosomiasis and soil-transmitted helminthiasis: Report of a WHO expert committee* (WHO Technical Report Series 912, pp. 1–57). Geneva.
- World Health Organization. (2021). *Soil-transmitted helminth infections fact sheet*. Retrieved from <http://www.who.int/mediacentre/factsheets/fs366/en/>

World Health Organization. (2021). *PCT Databank*. Retrieved from https://www.who.int/neglected_diseases/preventive_chemotherapy/databank/en/

World Health Organization. (2022). *Schistosomiasis fact sheet*. Retrieved from <http://www.who.int/mediacentre/factsheets/fs115/en/>

World Health Organization. (2022). *Vector control: Methods for use by individuals and communities*. Geneva.

Cite this article:

Author(s), KADRI, Adenike Koseganlola Risikat (RN, PhD), NGADI Yvette-Ella Adanna (RN, BNSc), OLALEYE, Christiana Oluwatoyi (RN, MSc), AYANLEKE, Ismail Adebare (RN, MSc), JIMOH, Esther Ozichu (RN, MSc), BELLO, Salihu Sule (RN, BNSc), (2025). " Perception and Acceptability Towards Administration of Anthelmintic Drugs to School Pupils Among Traders in Olomi Market, Ibadan", **Name of the Journal:** Commonwealth Journal of Academic Research, (CJAR.EU), P, 1- 13. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14641633> , Issue: 1, Vol.: 6, Article: 1, Month: January, Year: 2025. Retrieved from <https://www.cjar.eu/all-issues/>

Published by

AND

ThoughtWares Consulting & Multi Services International (TWCMSI)

